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Application of the Zoom Meeting Application in Online Learning During the Pandemic

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Abstract

In the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak, almost all Indonesians, including Bengkulu province, expect to experience the spike in positive cases of Covid-19, particularly in the Rejang Lebong Regency, resulting in many very significant changes in almost all fields, especially in the field of education. The learning process, consisting of synchronous learning, is carried out internet (online), namely face-to-face by video calls/ zoom meetings and asynchronous, namely by assignments. Using observational data methods, interviews, and notes, the research approach used is a qualitative research method. The aim of this study is to provide some explanations of the use of the zoom meeting application during a pandemic in online learning, to evaluate the constraints of using the zoom meeting application and the benefits of the application for zoom meeting from several features during a pandemic in online learning. The findings of this study show that it can be easier for lecturers and students to interact synchronously in the learning process by applying the zoom meeting application to learning during this pandemic.

Keywords: Zoom Application, Conference, Online Learning, Covid-19 Pandemics

PRELIMINARY

Currently the Covid-19 pandemic that is taking place in Indonesia has caused many very significant transformations in almost all fields to experience the negative impact of the conditions experienced in the current pandemic conditions (Atsani, 2020). The surge in positive cases of Covid-19 is also felt in the economic sector and in the field of education, there are many changes that have occurred at this time. The spread of the inclusion of the Covid-19 virus in Indonesia, especially in Bengkulu province, Rejang Lebong district, has made related institutions and governments have to present other ways in the learning process. Therefore, in education this creates a new system in terms of providing material for the learning process in order to keep education going well through synchronous and asynchronous learning processes.

This online educational activity uses a synchronous education system and asynchronous. In the application of the learning process, for now, there are only two options, namely synchronous and asynchronous learning, because

the learning process requires the learning process to adjust to practicing learning from home via online media. It is not uncommon for students, educators, lecturers, students and moreover parents to be so unprepared, because the education system, which initially studied face-to-face, is now all done online. Starting with the existence of a policy from the government that requires working from home, studying from home, or also worshipping from home. This situation requires learning institutions to continue implementing the latest innovations in the educational process. One form of this innovation is by implementing education online (Astini, 2020).

Online learning, of course, requires media as a means of learning both in schools and colleges, of course, by using various applications to facilitate the delivery of learning material. Some of these applications include zoom meetings, google Classroom, Jitsi Meet, Google Meet, Whatsapp and so on (Haqien & Rahman, 2020). According to (Indiani, 2020) The various media that have been presented in several applications are not certain to create optimal output. There are many aspects that must be prepared in the online media education process so that it can be maximized, not only from the readiness of educators but the selection of applications in online media is an important factor in the implementation of the learning process.

This learning is so that it can be synchronized into the presentation and explanation of the material, namely through the zoom application. Zoom is a free HD application with video and screen sharing for up to 100 people and even more and is also a learning medium using video and audio. And this application can also be used in a variety of mobile devices, laptops, and netbooks, so for now the zoom meeting application is an option for lecturers and students alike. Thus, from this application, lecturers can ensure their students take part in learning at the same time, even though in different places.

The use of information technology is very helpful in the learning process during the Covid-19 pandemic (Astini, 2020). Because since the beginning of the pandemic that occurred in Indonesia, many universities and schools have started using this online learning system. One of the colleges that uses an online learning system, namely the Curup State Islamic Institute (IAIN), is currently implementing a learning system through the Zoom Meetings application. The teaching and learning system uses the Zoom application via a smart phone or computer device. This system is carried out to anticipate the spread of the covid-19 virus in Rejang Lebong Regency, Curup so that the learning system can continue to run smoothly even though using online media.

This study aims to determine how to apply the zoom application in online learning during the pandemic to educators or lecturers who teach at the Curup State Islamic Institute (IAIN). In online learning activities by utilizing the zoom meeting application, according to (Haqien & Rahman, 2020) there are two theories that can review the learning activity process, namely about changing behavior seen from an experience and emphasizing the formation of behavior seen from the learning process. This theory in education also becomes a foundation in the learning process. Because in the learning process, of course, communication is definitely carried out by the lecturer and the student or the student and the lecturer in the learning process through the zoom meeting application.

There have been many studies that have examined the application, constraints and advantages of the zoom meeting application, but each region must have its own method and problems in using the application. Research conducted by (Hutauruk & Sidabutar, 2020) entitled *Obstacles to Online Learning During the Pandemic Period Among Mathematics Education Students: A Descriptive Qualitative Study* examines the obstacles faced by students during the online learning process at a private tertiary institution in North Sumatra. The findings of the research are that the obstacles faced by students are fundamental, including obstacles in the field of internet networks, limited features of online learning applications, and obstacles in terms of learning services.

The obstacles that are owned by this zoom meeting application are in addition to the internet network. However, it is also related to their involvement during the learning process, namely the expenditure of large internet quotas, and difficulties in the monitoring process or the process of developing student understanding related to the material that has been delivered by the lecturer. These findings can be related to the research by the author because in this discussion it is not only the problem of internet network problems but how to monitor the

development of student understanding regarding the presentation of the material that has been delivered by the lecturer.

The next research article by (Nasir, Bagea, Herlina, & Safitri, 2020) with the title Maximizing the "Breaking Rooms" Feature in Early Childhood Education during the Covid-19 Pandemic, in this study only aims to compile a guide for setting breakout rooms for teachers in maximize the use of the zoom meeting application, and conduct due diligence. From these findings, it can be related to findings from researchers about the advantages of several features possessed by the zoom meeting application in the learning process during a pandemic, apart from the breaking rooms feature.

An article by (Herawati, Gulyanto, & Sudarti, 2020) entitled Application of Zoom Application to Indonesian Language Student Speaking Skills Material that using the zoom meeting application is applied to speaking skills material for students of the Indonesian language and literature education process and this application was applied when the Indonesian government decided to make rules for the whole community to keep their distance and not hold mass activities anywhere. And in this study students must be able to use the zoom application properly, so that the material presented by the lecturer can be understood and applied in life. So that in this case there needs to be an understanding and also understand how to implement the zoom meeting application.

The need for each of the research journals that have been previously mentioned is related to a collection of theories and references that either support or do not support research. The several journals that were collected were shown so that the research carried out became stronger, because the content contained in each journal could be used as a reference. Thus, it can be concluded that the research to be carried out is relatively new and has not been much done by previous researchers.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a qualitative descriptive research that aims to examine the condition of natural objects and emphasize understanding the deep meaning of a symptom (Sugiyono, 2018). And also using the interview method, observation and documentation. This research is a research that is used to collect information and data with the help of a variety of materials sourced from journals and from books. To support the data, interviews, observations and in-depth documentation were conducted to several lecturers at the Curup State Islamic Institute (IAIN). So that the purpose of this study is to determine the application of the zoom meeting application in online learning during a pandemic, the constraints of using the zoom meeting application in online learning during a pandemic and the advantages of the zoom meeting application apart from being used in virtual terms in learning from during the pandemic at the Islamic Institute of Religion. Negeri (IAIN) Curup.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The spread of the covid-19 virus in Indonesia has had a major impact on the education sector. So that from many provinces, including Bengkulu province, the related institutions and government must present other ways in the learning process. Activities that involve large numbers of people are now starting to be limited, especially in Rejang Lebong district. The government has urged for now in learning activities both at school and in other universities and also activities such as meetings or seminars to still use the online system until the issuance of the latest circular so as not to increase the number of patients exposed to Covid-19.

The Minister of Education and Culture, Nadiem Makarim, followed up on circular number 4 of 2020, concerning the implementation of education policies in the emergency period of the spread of Covid-19. In this case the second point states, the learning process from home is carried out with the following conditions: a) Learning from home through online/distance learning is carried out to provide meaningful learning experiences for students without being burdened by the demands of completing all curriculum achievements for grade promotion and graduation; b) Learning from home can be focused on life skills education, including regarding the Covid-19 pandemic; c) Activities and learning assignments from home may vary between students including considering gaps in access to learning from home, d. Evidence or products of learning activities from home are given

qualitative and useful feedback from the teacher, without being required to give a score or quantitative value (Menteri Pendidikan, 2020).

This learning process system must also be balanced with an increase in lecturer competence. The students faced by lecturers today are millennial generation students who are aware of the existence of technology, therefore lecturers must also be required to always improve scientific competence and carry out innovations or updates on educational procedures. And while students have to improve their readiness to learn independently because online learning uses more self-directed learning, so students' self-directed learning becomes important (Wilson, 2020).

Online learning is divided into two, namely synchronous learning and asynchronous. In implementing the learning process, for now there are only two options, namely synchronous and asynchronous learning, because in the education level it requires the learning process to adapt to implementing learning from home through online media. Learning online can use digital technology such as applications that help guide the learning process such as zoom meetings, google meet, google classroom, or even live chat and so on. But what is certain to be done is by giving assignments or what is called asynchronous learning through monitoring mentoring by lecturers via WhatsApp group so that students or students really do their job.

The discussion of research data is obtained in the form of interview data, observation, documentation and also some literature references from journals through this data. The discussion formulation of the application of the zoom meeting application in online learning during the pandemic is divided into three aspects. the first aspect, regarding how to apply the zoom meeting application in learning, the second aspect, the constraints of using the zoom meeting application in online learning during the pandemic, and the third aspect of the advantages of using the zoom meeting application in online learning during the pandemic, focused on several features that facilitate the learning process online.

1. Application of zoom meeting application in online learning during pandemic.

Online learning is a learning process that is electronic or online-based. One of the media used in online learning can be via a smartphone or android and a computer developed in the form of a web, so that it is then developed into a wider computer network, namely the internet so that the presentation of the online learning process can run interactively (Suhery, Putra, & Jasmalinda, 2020).

In dealing with this new normal era, various efforts were made by the Curup State Islamic Institute (IAIN) campus so that the learning process continues to run effectively and interactively. So in this case, that the learning carried out by lecturers and students carries out video conferences using the zoom meeting application media. According to, Mr Dr. Fakhruddin M.Pd.I as the Director of Postgraduate who is also a lecturer at IAIN Curup stated that the application of the zoom meeting application in learning can be understood that learning in this network is done indirectly because we use the internet network with certain applications for transformation and communication. in learning. In fact, online learning has been around for a long time or has been used frequently for several courses and at other universities. Meanwhile, at the IAIN Curup campus, it happened that during this pandemic period it was finally forced to post online learning.

The process of applying zoom meeting media in the learning process is almost applied in every subject on the Curup State Islamic Institute (IAIN) campus. In the application of the zoom meeting application in a process it is necessary to prepare a syllabus, RPS, then prepare teaching materials to be shared with students via WhatsApp group, then to go through the learning process using the zoom meeting application so that in this pandemic period it is effective to use the zoom meeting application media. Meanwhile, according to Mrs. Asri Karolina, M.Pd.I, in the learning process it is necessary to make an attendance list using google form and create a zoom link to make it easier for students to enter the zoom meeting. So that the application of the use of the zoom meeting application is by first explaining to students then students participate to respond and explain and present the results of their observations or interviews. So that in addressing this, what encourages researchers to be

interested in examining how the application of the zoom meeting application in online learning during a pandemic.

So it can be concluded that the application of the zoom meeting application in online learning makes it easier for students and lecturers to implement learning. First, what must be done in the online learning process through the zoom meeting application is to create a link to share with students via the whatsapp group. Second, allowing students to click the zoom link to enter the zoom meeting with the approval of the meeting host. Third, lecturers begin to share learning materials to be discussed together according to the material contained in the syllabus and RPS. Then for each course there must be a division of groups so that it requires groups to present the material to be delivered so that students remain active in the learning process.

2. Constraints from using the zoom meeting application in online learning during the pandemic

Every application of zoom media that is applied to each course must have obstacles which are the main factors, such as students having difficulty getting an internet network, internet quota is increasingly wasteful, and so on (Herawati, Gulyanto, & Sudarti, 2020). Meanwhile, according to Mr Dr. Fakhruddin, M.Pd.I, of course, has become a common problem, namely the network. Because sometimes different cards or the use of these cards also cause difficulties when holding a zoom meeting such as "why don't you come in?", There is a problem in the signal, then difficulties in the monitoring process or the process of developing student understanding related to the material that has been delivered. Then the independence of students in the lecture process, sometimes students are also constrained when they want to provide the media. So that the need for understanding and the ability of students to carry out online lectures does not occur in terms of their competence. But the problem is with the network. The same thing was stated by (Haqien & Rahman, 2020) that the use of the zoom meeting application has several obstacles, namely the signal is not supportive for students who do not use a wifi signal and frequent strange sound disturbances that interfere with learning activities when turning on the voice. So it can be concluded that in using this zoom application there are obstacles, namely the most dominant in the application or use of the zoom meeting application in online lectures, this is a signal that is sometimes less supportive.

Meanwhile, according to (Anugrahana, 2020) that the problem with using the zoom meeting application is that when communicating via zoom, sometimes the signal is not smooth and the network becomes an obstacle in collecting tasks. Meanwhile, according to (Rosyid, Thohari, & Lismanda, 2020) the most dominant obstacle in using the zoom meeting application is dominated by user devices. Likewise, with the use of this application, of course there are several kinds of obstacles that can hinder the process of taking online lectures using the zoom meeting application. So it can be concluded that the most dominant obstacles in the application or use of the zoom meeting application in online lectures, including that many students are constrained by signals, large internet quota expenditures, and difficulties in the monitoring process or the process of developing student understanding related to it. with the material that has been delivered.

3. The advantages of using the zoom meeting application in online learning during a pandemic are focused on several features that make the learning process easier

Zoom Meeting is a communication application that uses various devices both cellular and desktop and in this application is also used to conduct face-to-face remotely with a large number of participants. The zoom meeting application also has its advantages, there are several features that make it easier for users in the learning and teaching process, including:

a. Video and Audio Features

This zoom application has video and audio that has the resulting image and sound quality because it is supported by high definition or HD quality. So that according to (Mustopa & Hidayat, 2020) in this application it can be used so that lecturers can see students while teaching and can interact via audio voice.

With the ease of application, lecturers and students are trained to be more creative and active in carrying out the learning process during a pandemic.

b. Share Screen feature

This share screen feature can make it easier for lecturers and students to share or present material in the form of power points, words and so on so that in this case they can display presentation slides through this feature.

c. Breaking Rooms feature

According to (Chandler, 2016) that breaking rooms are virtual spaces that are separate from the main room on the zoom meeting application. With breaking rooms, lecturers can provide more personal time for students to carry out activities, discuss together and facilitate work independently. In addition, lecturers can also enter the "room" if students need clarification or support about an assignment so that the interaction in this feature can also provide a peer-to-peer learning experience which is very valuable for building a solid group. By dividing students into small groups, this will reduce the distance between lecturers and students. So it can be concluded that the Breaking Rooms feature makes it easier for lecturers and students who are in the zoom to easily discuss and share in groups.

d. Security Features

In this zoom there is an end-to-end encryption feature that can be used by all meeting participants via the zoom application, making the security of its users unquestionable because additional security can be obtained from a password that only the user knows the password for, then recordings and transcripts in In this zoom, meeting participants can also record meetings that are zoomed in so that they can be saved on their respective devices or on a cloud account.

e. Scheduling Features

This zoom application can also schedule video conferencing to be carried out according to the agenda or activities so that users can start a video conference or meeting through their Outlook, Gmail, or iCal account.

So that in some of these explanations, the features contained in this zoom application make it easier for everyone to use them, starting from arranging meeting agendas or video conferences as well as in managing the learning process that makes it easier for lecturers and students to continue to be able to teach and learn in the current pandemic situation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research above, the researcher concludes that in the application of the zoom meeting application, steps are needed in the use of the zoom meeting application in the online learning process. This can make it easier for lecturers and students to transform and communicate in the learning process through the zoom meeting application. And based on the discussion of this zoom meeting application, it is quite appropriate, because even though long distance lecturers and students can carry out synchronous learning activities in online learning during this pandemic. Whereas in terms of constraints, there are several types of obstacles that are most dominant in the application or use of the zoom meeting application in online lectures, including many of the students are constrained by signals, large internet quota expenditures, and difficulties in the monitoring or processing process. development of student understanding related to the material that has been delivered. In addition, in using the zoom application, it turns out that this application also has advantages, namely it has several features including HD video and audio, share screen features, breaking rooms, security features, recording and transcription features, scheduling features between teams that can make it easier for users. in carrying out the learning process activities.

References

- Anugrahana, A. (2020). *Hambatan, Solusi dan Harapan: Pembelajaran Daring Selama Masa Pandemi Covid-19 Oleh Guru Sekolah Dasar*. *Scolaria: Jurnal Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan*, Vol. 10 No. 3.
- Astini, N. S. (2020). Pemanfaatan Teknologi Informasi dalam Pembelajaran Tingkat Sekolah Dasar pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Jurnal Lampuhyang LPM STKIP Vol. 11 No. 2*, 24.
- Atsani, L. M. (2020). Transformasi Media Pembelajaran Pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Vol.1 No.1* , 82.
- Chandler. (2016). Using Breakout Rooms in Synchronous Online Tutorials. *Jurnal of Perspective in Applied Academic Practise*, 16.

- Haqien, D., & Rahman, A. A. (2020). Pemanfaatan zoom meeting untuk proses pembelajaran pada masa pandemi covid-19. *Vol. 5 No. 1*, 52.
- Herawati, T., Gulyanto, B., & Sudarti, N. (2020). *Penerapan Aplikasi Zoom pada Materi Keterampilan Berbicara Mahasiswa Bahasa Indonesia*. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Multidisiplin Ilmu Universitas Asahan ke-4 .
- Hutauruk, A., & Sidabutar, R. (2020). Kendala Pembelajaran Daring Selama Masa Pandemi di Kalangan Mahasiswa Pendidikan Matematika:ajian Kualitatif Deskriptif. *Sepren: Journal of Mathematics Education and Applied, Vol. 2, No. 1*, 50.
- Indiani, B. (2020). Mengoptimalkan Proses Pembelajaran Dengan Media Daring Pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Vol. 1 No. 3 Tahun 2020*, 227.
- Menteri Pendidikan. (2020). *Surat Edaran Nomor 3 Tahun 2020 Tentang Pelaksanaan Pendidikan dalam Masa Darurat Corona Virus (covid-19)*.
- Mustopa, A. J., & Hidayat, D. (2020). Pengalaman Mahasiswa Saat Kelas Online Menggunakan Aplikasi Zoom Cloud Meeting Selama Covid-19. *Jurnal Digital Media & Relationship, Vol. 2 No. 2*, 82.
- Nahar. (2016). Penerapan Teori Belajar Behavioristik dalam Proses Pembelajaran. *vol. 1, No. 1*, 3.
- Nasir, Bagea, I., Herlina, B., & Safitri, A. (2020). Memaksimalkan Fitur Breaking Rooms Zoom Meeting pada Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini di Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Jurnal Obsesi: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini, Vol. 5, No. 1*, 612.
- Pakpahan, R., & Fitriani, Y. (2020). Analisa Pemnfaatan Informasi Dalam Pembelajaran Jarak Jauh di Tengah Pandemi Virus Corona Covid-19. *Vol. 4 No. 2*, 31.
- Rosyid , M. N., Thohari, I., & Lismanda, F. Y. (2020). *Penggunaan Aplikasi Zoom Cloud Meetings dalam Kuliah Statistik Pendidikan di Fakultas Agama Islam Universitas Islam Malang* . Malang: Vol. 5 No.11.
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: Alfabeta, CV.
- Suhery, Putra, J. T., & Jasmalinda. (2020). Sosialisasi Penggunaan Aplikasi Zoom Meeting dan Google Clasroom pada Guru di SDN 17 Mata Air Padang Selatan. *JIP (Jurnal Inovasi Penelitian), Vol. 1, No. 3*, 130.
- Wilson, A. (2020). *Penerapan Metode Pembelajaran Daring (Online) Melalui Aplikasi Berbasis Android Saat Pandemi Global* . : SAP (Sususnan Artikel Pendidikan) Vol. 5 No. 1.